

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Interventions in the final phase of elimination and prevention of re-establishment

Section

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Title

Targeted test and treat at point of entry (border screening) to reduce importation of human malaria parasites: a systematic review

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Targeted test and treat at point of entry (border screening) to reduce importation of human malaria parasites: a systematic review

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SUMMARY OF FINDINGS TABLE**Should testing and treatment at points of entry (border screening) vs. no intervention be used for reducing the number of imported cases?**

Testing and treatment at point of entry (border screening) compared to no intervention for reducing the number of imported cases

Outcome	Nº of participants (studies)	Certainty	Impact
Prevalence of infection among the group targeted by the intervention (test done at POE)	(1 observational study) ¹	⊕○○○ Very low ^a	Results indicate the highest prevalence in passengers younger than 15 years old travelling in the direction from the mainland to Bioko, 70.4% (95% CI 58.4 - 80.7; p-value 0.017). A lower prevalence was observed for the same age range in the opposite direction, 38.1% (95% CI 26.1 - 51.2; p-value 0.017). For passengers older than 15 years a prevalence of 35.7% (95% CI 30.1 - 41.6; p-value 0.001) was observed between the mainland and Bioko and a prevalence of 22.6% (95% CI 17.3 - 28.6; p-value 0.001) in the opposite direction.
Prevalence (positivity rate) of infection among the group targeted by the intervention (test done at POE)	0 cases 0 controls (4 observational studies) ^{2,3,4,5}	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b,c}	For UAE, where indigenous cases were zero, importation among arrivals applying for resident or work permits was between 4.6 and 9.1% for the study period. In Myanmar, among migrant workers, the positivity rate decreased over the years from 13.1% to 3.1%. In Cambodia, official border points identified different positivity rates depending on the neighbouring country, 0.6% with Thailand, 3.6% with Vietnam and 11.5% with Laos. Mobile malaria posts identified a decrease in the positivity rate over the years, from 9.2% to 0.09%.
Prevalence (positivity rate) of infection among the group targeted by the intervention (test done after entry)	(2 observational studies) ^{6,7}	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,c}	Results in Shanglin County, China, showed a positivity rate of 21.6%. Targeted test and treat was done to persons with overseas travel history, mainly coming from Ghana where they work in the gold mining sector, within an 8-day median interval (range 0-28 days; interquartile range 4-18 days) between return date and diagnosis date. Results in Evrotas area in Greece, showed a positivity rate of 1.6% in 2012 and 2015, 1.4% in 2016 and 1.5% in 2017. During 2013 and 2014 there were no cases because an MDA was implemented in the area. The median time period from the migrants arriving in Greece to the day of their first contact with the field team and their registration in the database was much higher for the years 2012–2014 (90, 60 and 10 days respectively), compared with the years 2015–2017 (5, 15 and 7 days respectively).

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References

¹Bradley, 2015; ²Stratil, 2021; ³Kheang, 2017; ⁴Edwards, 2015; ⁵Dar, 1993 ⁶Li,2015; ⁷Tseroni, 2020

Explanations

^aObservational study

^bBig differences among positivity rates (from 0.0 to 21.0)

^cOutcome expressed in positivity rate no prevalence

RationaleDescription of the Condition

Malaria is an infectious disease caused by different species of the *Plasmodium* parasite, which affects nearly half of the population in approximately 90 countries around the world. In 2019 it was estimated that 229 million cases and 409,000 deaths were disproportionately distributed around the globe¹. Vast global efforts and large economic investments have been made worldwide to reduce, control and eliminate malaria, resulting in a great reduction of the incidence in the last 20 years, from 238 million cases and 736,000 deaths in 2000² to the present numbers. Nevertheless, the reduction of cases and deaths seem to have slowed down from 2016, therefore, malaria remains a global public health issue³.

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines elimination as the 'reduction to zero incidences of indigenous cases of a specific malaria parasite species in a defined geographic area'. The path towards malaria elimination is a continuous process and differs within a country or area⁴, and after elimination, continued measures are required to prevent re-establishment of transmission.

The combination of strategies used for many years to decrease transmission to low levels such as vector control, efficient case management, and active surveillance, might not be the ideal ones to move from controlled low-endemic malaria to elimination. Different settings within a country or subnational area might need to adjust the interventions to a different target population (for example, adult and men instead of pregnant women and children), location (such hard-to-reach populations), or particular contexts (like migrants or imported malaria) to progress towards no local transmission^{5,6}.

Three types of interventions can be combined to accelerate towards malaria elimination: accelerator, targeted, and reactive strategies, which need to be tailored to the local context. Each intervention has a different objective and is deployed in different circumstances.

Accelerator interventions are usually put in place across a large geographic area to reduce transmission intensity to a level that intensive surveillance is feasible. Targeted strategies, put their focus on high-risk groups that might not be able to benefit from routine interventions. Finally, reactive strategies target new individual cases in settings in which the occurrence of malaria cases is very low^{7,8}.

Description of the Intervention

Understanding of high-risk populations and identification of where the resources are most needed or most likely to have the greatest effect are requisites to establish targeted interventions⁹. Actually, many countries fight their last few malaria cases before elimination along international borders, when these are shared with countries that have not achieved elimination and have sustained malaria transmission. For this reason, in 2018 WHO recommended by the Malaria Policy Advisory Group, convened an Evidence Review Group (ERG) on border malaria with the objective to summarize the factors that might influence transmission in these areas, to examine the effectiveness of current tools and draw evidence from other global/eradication initiatives¹⁰. The ERG concluded that there is no universal approach to

address border malaria, therefore countries should consider this problem early in order to shorten the long tail of elimination¹¹.

Why is the review important

Targeted test and treat (TTaT) at points of entry (border screening) which is testing populations crossing ports of entry between countries or regions of a country with a parasitologic test and treating confirmed malaria cases to reduce the number of imported infections in the eliminating country⁷, is one of the existing strategies to fight border malaria. Nevertheless, no evidence has been systematically collected and evaluated to know the impact of this strategy or to assess the benefits and harms of targeted test and treat compared to no targeted test and treat.

Objectives

The main objective of this work was to carry out a comprehensive, updated and systematic review of all available evidence regarding targeted test and treat strategies for malaria at point of entry to assess the relative effects (benefits and harms) of this intervention on human malaria transmission, when applied to people entering a country or subnational area, compared to no targeted test and treat at point of entry.

Specifically, the aims of this review were:

- To determine the benefits and harms of testing adults and children as they enter or return to a country or subnational area (not at some later time) for work, military service, residence, tourism or to visit friends and relatives (VFR) and treating confirmed cases with a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine including radical treatment for *Plasmodium vivax* (Pv) and *Plasmodium ovale* (Po).
- To identify evidence on contextual factors including values and preferences; acceptability; health equity; resource use and feasibility.
- To determine which factors are likely to have an epidemiological impact on the effectiveness of the intervention (potential effect modifiers¹) stated in **Table 1**.

The benefits and harms assessed are outlined in the outcome section in **Table 1** and classified by community level and among the group targeted by the intervention.

The ultimate goal of this systematic review was to provide evidence to support the development of recommendations related to the activities around border screening that countries should undertake to achieve elimination beyond case management and vector control.

Table 1. Description of the settings, Population Intervention Comparison Outcome (PICO) question for Targeted Test and Treat at point of entry.

Review question: *What are the relative effects (benefits and harms) of targeted test and treat at point of entry compared to no targeted test and treat at point of entry in adults and*

¹ Potential effect modifiers (PEM): malaria parasite species (Pf, Pv, Po or Pm in the area, antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide and hypnozoiticide, low versus high ratio of imported to indigenous cases, and limit of detection and sensitivity of the test.

children entering or returning to a country or subnational area for work, military service, residence, tourism or to visit friends and families?

Setting	Point of entry (border crossing, airport, seaport) in an area with ongoing malaria transmission seeking to eliminate malaria or an area with malariogenic potential seeking to prevent re-establishment
Population²	Adults and children entering or returning to a country or subnational area for work, military service, residence, tourism or to visit friends and families
Intervention	Parasitologic testing and treatment of confirmed cases
Comparison	No intervention
Outcome (in priority order)	Community level 1. Number of positive cases found as a proportion of total imported cases Among the group targeted by the intervention: 1. Adverse events 2. Prevalence of infection

METHODS

Eligibility criteria

Setting characteristics

The study characteristics for eligibility were specific to the PICO descriptors listed in **Table 1**. Studies selected were research that had taken place in an area with ongoing malaria transmission seeking to eliminate malaria or an area with malariogenic potential seeking to prevent re-establishment.

Type of participants

The malaria affected population included adults and children entering or returning to a country or subnational area with ongoing malaria transmission seeking to eliminate malaria or an area with malariogenic potential seeking to prevent re-establishment for work, military service, residence, tourism or to visit friends and relatives.

Type of interventions

1. *Intervention arm:* For the purpose of this review, targeted test and treat (TTaT) at point of entry was defined as parasitologic testing (with or without prior symptom screening) for malaria infection with human *Plasmodium spp.* followed by treatment of confirmed

² The population is the group targeted by the intervention. However, the benefits of the intervention are intended to apply to the wider community by reducing importation and transmission of malaria. Therefore, outcomes will be measured at both the community level and at the level of the individuals targeted by the intervention.

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cases with a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine including treatment for liver stage parasites for infections caused by *P. vivax* and *P. ovale*. Therefore, studies in which interventions were compounded with other interventions such as reactive strategies, mass drug administration (MDA), targeted drug administration (TDA), or mass test and treat (MTaT) were excluded.

2. *Control arm*: No TTaT at point of entry.
3. *Background interventions*: We anticipated that existing control efforts would include background interventions that provide adequate access to case management, testing and treatment for the populations within an intervention area. We documented the standard of care for the place at that time, where possible. Similarly, for studies in areas that had individual-level chemoprevention strategies as part of their standard of care, we documented the details on time and duration of these interventions, if available.

Types of studies

The study designs eligible for inclusion to assess the balance of benefits and harms were observational studies and non-randomized studies. We expected that it would be unlikely to identify randomized trials given the scope of intervention. However, if trials were identified they would have been included. Additionally, for the assessment of contextual factors (i.e. values and preferences; acceptability; health equity and human rights; resource implications and feasibility and health system considerations) relevant to implementation and operational aspects of the intervention, qualitative studies were also included. Eligible study designs that were included are highlighted in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Inclusion criteria for type of study designs.

Type of study design	Additional requirements
Qualitative study designs	
Observational study designs Prospective Retrospective	<i>Cohort, Case-Control or Cross-Sectional Surveys.</i>
Non-randomized study designs	
Quasi-experimental cluster controlled trials	<i>At least 2 clusters per arm.</i>
Controlled before and after studies	<i>At least two sites per arm. Contemporaneous control group.</i>
Interrupted time series (ITS), controlled or not	<i>Intervention occurs at a defined point in time. At least 3 data points collected over one year before and 3 data points collected one year post-intervention.</i>
Uncontrolled before and after studies Before and after studies with historical controls	<i>Note: These studies will be judged to have a critical risk of bias.</i>
Mathematical modeling studies	
Simulations with mathematical modeling Mathematical models based on empirical data	<i>Inclusion criteria will be the same as for empirical studies.</i>

Mathematical modelling studies grounded in empirical data from specific study sites	
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Exclusion criteria

This review was focused on TTaT at point of entry and did not include studies aimed to assess or evaluate the efficacy of antimalarials, drug regimens/ dosing, or diagnostic tests. Likewise, we did not include studies that assessed the supply chain, resource management, access to care, and quality of care. While we were aware that these all play a significant role in overall intervention effectiveness, we did not individually assess these program characteristics. Rather, these attributes of the corresponding country’s health system were to be considered when assessing the success of the control strategy given the public health conditions that surrounded service delivery by the guidelines development group (GDG) when interpreting the results of this systematic review for interpretation in the evidence to decision-making process.

Studies were excluded if:

- Follow-up periods for intervention and control arms were not the same, or timing of baseline and endline surveys was not at the same time in intervention and control arms, or the length of pre- and post-intervention periods for ITS studies were different (or covered different seasons).
- Background interventions are not equally implemented between intervention and control arms.
- There were other interventions implemented at the same time in the intervention arm but not the control arm.

Outcomes

The outcomes assessed for the targeted test and treat at point of entry strategy included variables measured both among the high-risk population and at the population level, as well as adverse events measured only among those receiving the intervention. Studies had to report at least one or more of the outcomes included in **Table 3**, data on contextual factors, or mathematical modelling results. For outcomes that specified parasitological confirmation, the possible diagnostic approaches included malaria rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), microscopy, or molecular methods such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

Table 3. Outcome measures for Targeted Test and Treat studies at point of entry.

Community level	Number of positive cases found as a proportion of total imported cases
Targeted group	Adverse events Prevalence of infection

Contextual factors

For the assessment of the evidence of contextual factors relevant to implementation and operational aspects of the intervention, all study designs, including qualitative studies were included. The following contextual factors were assessed :

- *Values and preferences*: The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention;
- *Acceptability*: extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention.
- *Health equity and human rights*: extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all.
- *Resource use*: cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit.
- *Feasibility*: legal barriers to implementation, interaction with the existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce or other resources or programmatic considerations.

Modeling Studies

Modeling studies were used to provide evidence for operational considerations, such as timing of the intervention, coverage rates, number of rounds, etc. These studies were further categorized as:

- *Simulation mathematical studies based on assumptions*
- *Mathematical modeling studies grounded in empirical data from specific study sites*

Information sources

The studies included in this review were identified by searching in academic publications, relevant electronic databases and the grey literature without timeframe limitation. Pre-defined search terms and relevant subheadings were used, as well as keywords for malaria, antimalarial, screening, diagnosis, treatment and borders.

The following sources were included¹²:

- Bibliographic databases: MEDLINE (PubMed), LILACS, EMBASE (Ovid), the Cochrane Library.
- Other relevant databases: ZETOC, Armed Forces Pesticide Management Board (AFPMB), The Archives of the World Health Organization, US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (clinicaltrials.gov), ISRCTN registry, The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP), and the MESA Track database.

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- Conference proceedings: American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) Annual Meetings, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health Future of malaria research Symposium, Keystone/MESA Symposium, Women in Malaria Conference, Doctors Without Borders (MSF) Scientific Days 2021, Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN) Journal Clubs (TechTalks), 6th Southern Africa Malaria Research Conference.
- Researchers and organizations within the field.
- Reference lists: the reference lists of studies identified and included in the review were reviewed for additional relevant studies.

All studies that met eligibility criteria regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress) were included for consideration in this review.

Search strategy

A preliminary search was conducted to scope the state of the art, assess appropriate search keywords and terms and collect background information on malaria elimination strategies. This scoping search strategy was developed in consultation with a librarian from the University of Barcelona.

The final search strategy for the review was developed in collaboration with a systematic review information specialist and was conducted in March 2021. This final search strategy is presented in **Appendix 1**.

Data management

To manage records and data throughout the review, the software system Mendeley³ was used for the storage of identified articles. Corresponding shared spreadsheets and documents were stored using G-suite tools. The overall project details for studies included in the reviews are stored in the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance (MESA) tracking tool (MESA Track⁴). In addition, ongoing projects have been compiled in MESA Track as a “Deep Dive” to allow for reference to projects that may generate relevant results in the future. The title/abstract and full-text reviews were conducted in Eppi-Reviewer 4.0 and Eppi-Reviewer Web. All data extracted from selected studies were recorded in an excel spreadsheet and the outcome data and analyses were conducted in Eppi-Reviewer 4.0 and Eppi-Reviewer Web⁵.

³ Mendeley is a company based in London, UK, which provides products and services for academic researchers. It is most known for its reference manager which is used to manage and share research papers and generate bibliographies for scholarly articles. Website: www.mendeley.com

⁴ MESA Track is a living database which captures research projects and institutions’ portfolios in malaria elimination and eradication. The tool was developed and managed by the MESA Alliance, hosted at the Barcelona Institute for Global Health and funded by a grant from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Website: mesamalaria.org/mesa-track

⁵ Eppi-Reviewer is an application for literature reviews, including systematic reviews, meta-analyses, 'narrative' reviews and meta-ethnographies. The tool was developed and maintained by the EPPI-Centre at the Social Science Research Unit of the UCL Institute of Education, University of London, UK. Website: eppi.ioe.ac.uk. Eppi-Reviewer was last updated on 15 October 2020 (version 4.11.5.1).

Selection process

Two authors from the systematic review team independently reviewed abstracts and titles from the retrieved articles. For any discrepancies or disagreements in inclusion or exclusion by the two authors, the remaining systematic review team members assessed the title and abstract for agreement. All studies identified as potentially eligible based on the title and abstract reviews were retrieved, and the full report was assessed for eligibility by both authors, independently. The final selection for both the title/abstract screening and full-text screening was made using an eligibility criteria checklist to record how each study was assessed based on study inclusion/exclusion criteria. For any discrepancies or disagreements in inclusion by the two authors, the remaining systematic review team members assessed the study for inclusion. In the event of disagreement, the WHO methodologist and Elimination Guidelines Development team lead were consulted for final determination. The final list of studies included in the full-text review was shared with the GDG, WHO methodologist and malaria elimination team lead for agreement. The abstract/title screening process and full-text review processes were tested in a calibration exercise with the study authors using the Eppi-Reviewer 4.0 and/or Web tools. Each author practised the abstract/title screening and full-text review independently, followed by the development of a written standard operating procedure (SOP) to codify the screening process. The authors then conducted an exercise to compare the screening outcomes for the abstract/title and full-text review on a subset of articles using the corresponding SOPs in the Eppi-Reviewer tool.

After data extraction and categorization of study information we planned to assess any included RCTs for meta-analysis by the primary author with confirmation by a second review team member; potential for pooled analyses were based on outcome data and time points for the intervention and follow-up timeframe. **Figure A2.1 and Figure A2.2 in Appendix 2** represent the flow diagram for the review methodology and the adapted PRISMA flow diagram for study synthesis and meta-analysis.

Data collection process

Of the studies selected for inclusion in the review, key data was extracted from study documents by the primary author, with confirmation by the secondary authors by separately extracting data into an abridged data extraction table and comparing it with the data extracted by the primary author. For any information not specified in study documents, the principal investigators for the study were contacted for consultation on missing and additional information and asked to share further information. For data that could not be retrieved, missing data was not added by imputation methods, rather the study was assessed for an alternative qualitative summary analysis for specific outcomes with missing data.

Data items

The data extracted from the studies included both descriptive data and study calculations and measurements (where relevant) to assess comparability and eligibility for data synthesis and pooled analyses. Variables for data extraction included: study design, setting, demographics, methodology, treatment, comparison, time period, intervention, outcomes, study biases, background interventions, and any other contextual study information that was informative in assessing confidence as evidence. The review authors developed the data extraction forms to

capture the necessary study variables and conducted a practice exercise for the data collection process. Refer to **Table A2.3** in **Appendix 2** for summary of variables for extraction.

Study risk of bias assessment

The primary author independently assessed the risk of bias in individual studies included in the review, and a secondary author performed an abridged assessment at the domain level for comparison and agreement.

Different tools to assess the risk of bias were planned depending on the design of each study. For RCTs, the Cochrane 'Risk of bias' (RoB) RoB2 tool¹³ was used with an assessment reported as low risk, some concerns, high-risk, or unclear and with the results displayed as summary graphs. The RoB assessment would have been conducted at the outcome level for each study. The RoB2 tool for cluster randomized trials addresses the additional criteria described in section 23.1.2 in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions was used specifically for cluster-RCTs¹⁴. For non-randomized controlled trials and ITS trials, the 'Risk of bias' tool (ROBINS-I) from the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organization of Care (EPOC) Group¹⁵ was used with an assessment reported as low risk, moderate risk, serious risk, critical risk, or no information. If any domain reached a critical risk of bias, the assessment was discontinued, as further evaluation would not influence how the certainty of the evidence was assessed. All outcomes from uncontrolled before-and-after studies and before-and-after studies with historical controls were assigned a critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design¹². These studies were only included if there were no other studies available or if there were no other studies for an important subgroup. If these studies were included, a sensitivity analysis was conducted, assuming there were sufficient other studies, by conducting the meta-analysis without the studies with critical risk of bias and then conducting a sensitivity analysis by including them.

For all studies that were considered to be at critical risk of bias, a subsidiary descriptive analysis and report of their estimates of effect were generated. A sensitivity analysis was planned to be conducted for these studies to describe the effect of confounding¹².

The risk of bias assessments were conducted using predefined criteria for Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) as described in the Confidence assessment section below. Any disagreements or discrepancies between reviewers were resolved through discussion or by consulting the other systematic review members. If a consensus was not reached, the systematic review team consulted the WHO methodologist¹².

Effect measures

Synthesis methods

To decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis, we tabulated the study intervention characteristics and compared for each outcome. For data where a quantitative synthesis could be conducted, meta-analysis was planned to combine and summarize the results of the included studies.

For outcomes (e.g., infection, adverse events, etc.) of randomized studies, we planned to extract the crude number of cases, number of participants targeted in the intervention, those reporting

adverse events, and the total number of participants assessed for the outcome in each study arm. For each outcome the crude proportions or ratios were recorded, as well as the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm for incidence rates. Measures of variance (e.g. standard error, intercorrelation coefficient or coefficient of variance) were included if provided in the study methods. We recorded both crude and adjusted measures of effect (e.g. risk ratio (RR), odds ratio (OR), rate ratio (RR), or mean difference (MD)) with 95% confidence intervals (CI).

For non-randomized studies, we extracted crude data including number of cases, number of participants, and any measures from statistical analysis (e.g. results from t-tests-, chi-squared tests or other measures assessing significance of the outcomes for the targeted population) included in the study. Adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding including odds ratios or relative risk estimates from generalized regression models were also recorded. Where limited statistical analyses were available, we generated a narrative summary of the intervention and outcomes for each included study and reported any estimates for yield of the intervention in targeting the population of interest.

Data synthesis

We planned to pool data from randomized and non-randomized studies separately. We planned to use a random-effects meta-analysis to report a pooled effect estimate when appropriate. If there were only two studies available for synthesis, a fixed-effects meta-analysis was used if meta-analysis was appropriate. Due to the nature of the data reported in the studies, no statistical synthesis could be done. Rather, only narrative synthesis of studies with compatible outcomes were reported noting trends in yield or potential impact of the intervention in targeted populations. Seeing that of crude data provided in the studies and varied definitions for 'prevalence' across studies, positivity rate for the targeted populations were calculated to allow for a comparable measure across studies to facilitate the narrative summaries and outcome assessments.

Assessment of heterogeneity

To test for heterogeneity in the included studies we planned to use a chi-squared (χ^2) statistic test for study effect measures, assessing a P-value of <0.05 as significant. We also planned to assess heterogeneity using the degree of inconsistency (I^2) to calculate the percentage of total variation across studies that was not due to chance. The interpretation for inconsistency across study outcomes effect measures uses a scale of very low, low, moderate, or high with values of $<25\%$, $26-50\%$, $51-74\%$ and $>75\%$, respectively¹⁶. If there was substantial heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value above 50%) and inconsistency in the direction of the effect with non-overlapping CIs, then a meta-analysis was considered inappropriate. Rather, we planned to perform a subgroup analysis as described below to see if we could reduce heterogeneity. Given the lack of studies eligible for statistical synthesis, there was no need for an assessment of heterogeneity in the included studies.

Subgroup analysis

For the prioritized potential effect modifiers, it was planned that data would be stratified for subgroup analysis, with at least two studies in each subgroup. The subgroups to be assessed were:

- Malaria parasite species (Pf, Pv, Po or Pm) in the area
- Antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide and hypnozoiticide
- Low vs. high ratio of imported to indigenous cases
- Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test

Where quantitative synthesis was not appropriate, due to limited number of studies and inability to reduce substantial heterogeneity, the subgroup analysis was not performed and the resultant data has been summarized based on key findings in a narrative description. Likewise, for the contextual factors, it was planned that data would be stratified using the categories listed above and textually summarized.

Reporting bias assessment

Most reporting biases are accounted for within the approach used for the identification of studies for the review. Meta-biases such as selective reporting of bias were planned to be assessed in part by the RoB assessments being conducted at the study level and in the data extraction process, which allowed for the identification of gaps in reported outcomes across studies. In particular, for within study selective reporting bias for included randomized studies, if a trial registration was available, the registration was checked for consistency in methodology, outcomes planned and what was reported in the study. For publication bias, funnel plots were planned to be generated if there were at least 10 studies included in the analysis.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of the evidence for each intervention across each outcome measure was assessed using the GRADE method (**Table 4**). Randomized studies were planned to initially be ranked as high certainty of evidence and non-randomized studies were initially ranked as low. The certainty of evidence was downgraded if there was evidence of the following 1) risk of bias, 2) imprecision, 3) inconsistency of evidence, 4) indirectness and 5) publication bias. Certainty of evidence for non-randomized studies could be upgraded if all domains were rated as low risk and there was evidence of 1) large magnitude of effect, 2) evidence of a dose-response relationship, or 3) where it was likely that residual confounding would increase the magnitude of effect.

Table 4. Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) criteria.

Certainty	Interpretation
Very Low	The authors believe that the true effect is likely to be markedly different from the estimated effect
Low	The authors believe that the true effect might be markedly different from the estimated effect
Moderate	The authors believe that the true effect is probably close to the estimated effect
High	The authors have a lot of confidence that the true effect is similar to the estimated effect

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To ensure consistency in judgements around precision and size of absolute effect measures of interventions to reduce transmission, thresholds for determining public health value of interventions were determined. Since none of the studies included in the study required effect size determinations for summary of findings statements the certainty of evidence was based solely on the criteria described above.

For the contextual factors assessed in the review, we planned to use the 'Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research' (GRADE-CERQual) approach. The GRADE-CERQual approach provides a certainty or confidence of a qualitative synthesis of studies using the following four components: 1) the methodological limitations, 2) coherence, 3) the adequacy of data supporting a review finding, and 4) the relevance of data from primary studies¹⁸. We planned to assess and interpret each contextual factor using the criteria adapted from the descriptive interpretations by Lewin et al¹⁹. However, given the low number of studies included for contextual factors and the fact that no synthesis for contextual factors was possible, it was decided to only produce textual summaries of findings for each study.

Study selection

A total of 1435 records were identified: 1310 via searching databases, 28 from registers, and 97 via other methods (e.g., websites, organizations and citation searching). Before the screening, 244 records were removed due to duplication, with a total of 1191 records to be screened against title and abstract eligibility (1094 identified via databases and registers and 97 identified via other methods). Of these, 62 were assessed for full-text eligibility criteria. After the full-text screening, seven studies were included for assessment of outcome data, three studies were included for assessment of contextual factors and three were included for modelling. The detailed Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Flow Diagram is presented in **Appendix 3**, which also includes the reasons for exclusion.

Three studies appeared to meet the inclusion criteria but were excluded because they were still in progress with no published results (See [Ongoing studies](#)).

Study characteristics

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the [Characteristics of studies tables](#).

Included studies

Seven studies met the criteria for inclusion, all of them were nonrandomized observational studies, conducted in different areas. In Equatorial Guinea (**Bradley, 2015**²⁰), United Arab Emirates (**Dar, 1993**²¹), Myanmar (**Kheang, 2017**²²), China (**Li, 2015**²³), Greece (**Tseroni, 2020**²⁶) and two in Cambodia (**Edwards, 2015**²⁴ and **Stratil, 2021**²⁵). Three articles were assessed for contextual factors: two articles for acceptability (**Edwards, 2015**²⁴ and **O'Sullivan, 2011**²⁷) and one article for feasibility (**Stratil, 2021**²⁵). Additionally, three articles were assessed for modelling (**Silal, 2014**²⁸; **Silal, 2015**²⁹ and **Silal, 2015**³⁰).

Descriptive characteristics of the seven included studies are summarized in **Table 5** and described in detail in the [Characteristics of included studies tables](#).

Interventions

All seven studies described test and treat strategies targeted to specific populations. **Bradley, 2015** focused on testing by RDT passengers travelling by boat between Bioko Islands and Equatorial Guinea mainland. Participants testing positive were referred to a local clinic for appropriate antimalarial treatment. The targeted population in **Dar, 1993** were all new arrivals applying for resident or work permits into the United Arab Emirates, mainly the AL Ain district which shares a border with Oman. Testing was done by microscopy during a medical check-up, and all slide-positive cases were treated with standard chloroquine phosphate at the clinic. **Kheang, 2017** focused on migrants entering into or departing from endemic areas within Myanmar; the test was done in screening points at key fixed locations in Tanintharyi Region and in Kayin State, by temperature check and RDT. Adequate treatment was offered if necessary. Two related studies, **Edwards, 2015** part of the Pre-Regional Artemisinin Initiative (Pre-RAI) and **Stratil, 2021** performed within the Regional Artemisinin-resistance Initiative Two Elimination (RAI2E) project, occurred in the areas of Cambodia bordering Thailand, Laos and Vietnam in different periods of time. The test and treat intervention from **Edwards, 2015** was implemented

between 2013 and 2014 focusing on mobile and migrants' populations crossing the borders, with fever screening, RDT test and RT-PCR done at official border points. If positive, they were treated according to the Cambodian national treatment guidelines. On the other hand, **Stratil, 2021** implemented active case detection between 2018 and 2020, targeting remote populations living in forested border areas. An RDT test was done in mobile malaria posts at border crossing areas, at forest entry points or market places. Positive cases were treated with artemisinin-based combination therapy (artesunate-mefloquine with pyronaridine-artesunate) or primaquine. **Li, 2015** focused on people returning to China from overseas malaria-endemic regions, mainly Ghana, after the government of Ghana began to strictly regulate the gold mining industry, which forced many gold miners to return to Shanglin County within a short time. Active malaria screening was done by microscopy with a median interval between return date and diagnosis data of 8 days and treatment was facilitated when necessary: either artemisinin-based combination therapy, chloroquine with primaquine or chloroquine alone. In **Tseroni, 2020** the target population were migrants coming from endemic countries residing in Evrotas Municipality, southern Greece, and covered by the active case detection (ACD) program. Tests were done in the migrant households and the tools used were fever screening, RDT test, microscopy and PCR; the median time from arrival to registration was 90, 60, 15, 10 and 7 days respectively in 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2016. Positive cases were treated with directly observed therapy with chloroquine and primaquine (after G6PD testing).

Outcomes

A proxy for prevalence of infection among the targeted populations was reported in all seven studies. However, only **Bradley, 2015** reported the outcome as prevalence with a 95% CI and *p*-value. **Dar, 1993** mentioned the number examined by year and the number of positive cases. **Kheang, 2017** reported the numbers of total tested by fiscal year (October to September), the positive cases by fiscal year and the total malaria positive rate. **Edwards, 2015** reported the outcome as number of tests (RDT and RT-PCR), number of positive cases and positivity rate (%) with a 95% CI. **Stratil, 2021** mentioned number of people tested, *P. falciparum* cases detected and number of people tested to find 1 *P. falciparum* case. **Li, 2015** reported the outcome by number of persons screened for malaria, number of detected malaria infection and attack rate (%). **Tseroni, 2020** mentioned the median number (range) of migrants screened (during weekly or bimonthly visits) and number of reported malaria cases (imported or locally acquired).

Contextual Factors

The acceptability of targeted test and treat at point of entry was reported in **Edwards, 2015** and **O'Sullivan, 2011**²⁷. Feasibility of this intervention was assessed in **O'Sullivan, 2011** and **Stratil, 2021**.

Modelling Studies

Three modelling studies from the same author were identified **Silal, 2014**; **Silal, 2015** and **Silal, 2015**.

Excluded studies

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Fifty-five articles were excluded after full-text screening due to the following reasons: incorrect population (n = 14), incorrect intervention (n = 3), incorrect study focus area (n = 17), cross-referenced article (n = 7), incorrect outcome (n = 6) or because a full report could not be retrieved (e.g., abstract, protocol or other document and ongoing studies) (n = 8). All full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria are listed with their reasons for exclusion in the [Characteristics of excluded studies table](#).

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Table 5. Characteristics of included studies.

Study	Location	Year(s)	Study design	Intervention	Outcome reported
Bradley, 2015 ²⁰	Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea	2013	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: passengers traveling by boat from Equatorial Guinea mainland to Bioko and vice versa • Border control: tight • Intervention: test and treat • Diagnostic tool: RDT • Test conditions: on the boat 	Prevalence of infection among those.
Dar, 1993 ²¹	United Arab Emirates border with Oman	1988 - 1991	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: all new arrivals applying for resident or work permits • Border control: tight • Intervention: test and treat • Diagnostic tool: microscopy • Test conditions: medical check-up 	Prevalence of infection among those (<i>reported as n° of examined and n° of positive</i>).
Kheang, 2017 ²²	Myanmar	2012 - 2015	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: migrants entering into or departing from endemic areas • Border control: loose • Intervention: test and treat (active & passive case detection) • Diagnostic tool: temperature checked & RDT • Test conditions: screening points at key fixed locations 	Prevalence of infection among those (<i>reported as total tested and positive cases</i>).
Edwards, 2015 ²⁴	Cambodia border with Thailand, Laos and Vietnam	2013 - 2014	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: mobile and migrant populations crossing the borders • Border control: loose • Intervention: test and treat • Diagnostic tool: fever screening, RDT test & RT-PCR • Test conditions: official border points 	Prevalence of infection among those (<i>reported as positivity rate %, 95% CI</i>).
Stratil, 2021 ²⁵	Cambodia border with	2018 - 2020	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: remote populations living in forested border areas 	Prevalence of infection among those (<i>reported as</i>

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	Thailand, Laos and Vietnam			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Border control: loose • Intervention: proactive case detection and treat • Diagnostic tool: RDT test • Test conditions: mobile malaria posts at border crossings, at forest entry points or market places 	<i>n° of people tested and P. falciparum cases detected).</i>
Li, 2015 ²³	China	2013	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: people returning from overseas malaria-endemic regions, mainly Ghana • Border control: tight • Intervention: active malaria screening and treat • Diagnostic tool: microscopy • Test conditions: median interval time between return date and diagnosis date was 8 days. 	Prevalence of infection among those (<i>reported as attack rate %</i>).
Tseroni, 2020 ²⁶	Greece	2012 - 2017	Nonrandomized observational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted population: migrants from endemic countries residing in the area and covered by the program. • Border control: tight • Intervention: active case detection (ACD) and treat • Diagnostic tool: fever screening, RDT test, microscopy & PCR • Test conditions: migrant household / median time from arrival to registration was 90, 60, 15, 10, 7 and 5 days per year (between 2012 and 2017). 	Prevalence of infection among those (<i>reported as n° of migrants screened and n° of reported malaria cases</i>).

Risk of bias in studies

All nonrandomized observational studies (Bradley, 2015; Dar, 1993; Kheang, 2017; Edwards, 2015; Stratil, 2021, Li, 2015 and Tseroni, 2020) were assigned a critical overall risk of bias due to study design. For each study a descriptive analysis and report of their outcomes has been generated.

Results by individual study outcomes

Narrative Summaries

1. **Bradley, 2015:** Infection importation: a key challenge to malaria elimination on Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea

A key challenge to malaria elimination in Equatorial Guinea (EG) includes the increasing number of travelers between mainland EG and Bioko Island. Targeted strategies that aid in reducing the malaria burden in passengers arriving from the mainland should be considered for control measures to prevent persistent spread to and from the island. There was year-round transmission documented for *P. falciparum* infection in children ages 2-14 years with prevalence rates of 14%, 28% and 18% in 2012, 2012 and 2014, respectively. In the mainland EG by 2011 was identified a prevalence of 59%. To assess the amount of transmission taking place where border control is relatively tight, an observational cross-sectional study was conducted during border crossings via boat sailings from the mainland to the island. Testing and treatment of positive cases were implemented to identify individuals with *P. falciparum* infections during boat crossings once a week within the twice weekly sailings between Bata (EG Mainland) and Malabo (Bioko Island) for 1 month in December 2013. Passengers were tested using an RDT and offered treatment, if positive. Bioko has a population of approximately 250000, with approximately 21000 individuals arriving each month from the EG mainland during the 4 boat sailings per week.

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was prevalence among the group targeted by the intervention
- More positive cases were identified in travelers from the mainland to Bioko (**Table 6**)
- Greatest prevalence rates were identified in children under 15 years of age (**Table 6**)
- No contextual factors assessed. However, this is a costly approach, as it would entail screen and treat or presumptive treatment for all individuals arriving from the mainland.
- Impact and acceptability would need to be evaluated for implementation of targeted interventions

Table 6. Malaria prevalence in Bioko (for children > 2 but < 14 years old) and in in boat passengers.

<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in Bioko in children between 2 to 14 year old			
2004	2012	2013	2014
45%	14%	28%	18%

<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in passengers travelling from Bioko to the mainland and vice versa	
Under 15 years old	Aged 15 years or over

Direction of travel	Prevalence 95% CI p-value	Direction of travel	Prevalence 95% CI p-value
Bioko - ML	38.1% (63) 26.1 - 51.2 0.017	Bioko - ML	22.6% (226) 17.3 - 28.6 0.001
ML - Bioko	70.4% (71) 58.4 - 80.7 0.017	ML - Bioko	35.7% (283) 30.1 - 41.6 0.001

2. **Dar, 1993:** Status of imported malaria in a control zone of the United Arab Emirates bordering an area of unstable malaria

After a concerted effort to reduce importation of malaria and elimination of existing foci in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) the relative rate of indigenous malaria was reduced from 20.7% in 1983 to 2.8% in 1988. The vector species in the area are *An. culicifucies* and *An. Stephensi*. Even though the inland district of Al Ain was a consolidated area with no local malaria transmission across the undermarked border in Oman by 1993, transmission continued mostly during the optimal conditions between November and March. In an effort to reduce imported cases, targeted strategies were implemented in a country where there is tight border control. A nonrandomized observational study was executed to assess test and treat strategies implemented for all new arrivals applying for resident or work permit to identify *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae* or mix infections during 4 years, between 1988 to 1991. Testing was done by microscopy and all slide-positive cases of malaria were treated with the standard chloroquine phosphate dose of 600 mg base. Al Ain district is part of the Abu Dhabi Emirate with a predominantly non-national population of 212 000 centered around the city of Al Ain.

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was incidence of imported malaria among the group targeted by the intervention in the Al Ain district
- The number of positive cases (**Table 7**) remained high enough to threaten the introduction of imported malaria into the local *Anopheles spp.* mosquitoes if control measures were relaxed.
- No UAE national acquired the infection in that country.
- The principal sources of malaria were Pakistan and Oman, followed by Sudan and Iran.
- Chloroquine-resistant strains of *P. falciparum* (CRPF) were first encountered in the UAE in 1984, when 5 cases of Yemeni origin were found to be unresponsive to standard treatment. They had all acquired the infection in Kenya. Follow-up investigations in the Al Ain district showed a dramatic increase in such cases. In 1990, 7.86% of all imported *P. falciparum* infections were resistant to standard chloroquine therapy.

Table 7. Relative rate in the UAE and incidence of imported malaria.

Relative rate of indigenous malaria in UAE				
Year	1983	1987	1988	> 1988

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Relative rate	20.7%	7.1%	2.8%	0%
<i>Incidence of imported malaria in the Al Ain district, United Arab Emirates</i>				
Year	1988	1989	1990	1991
Nº examined	15732	18022	18532	16317
Nº positive	730 (5.9%)	936 (4.7%)	1282 (6.9%)	1483 (9.1%)

3. **Kheang, 2017:** Malaria Case Detection Among Mobile Populations and Migrant Workers in Myanmar: Comparison of 3 Service Delivery Approaches

A key population to contain the spread of artemisinin-resistant malaria in the border areas between Cambodia, Myanmar and Thailand are mobile populations and migrant workers. To fight these challenges, the Control and Prevention of Malaria (CAP-Malaria) Project sponsored by USAID and PMI was implemented by the University Research Co., LLC. between 2012 and 2016. Malaria season in Cambodia is between May/June to October and the border control is loose. A nonrandomized observational study was conducted to assess the amount of transmission taking place in these three borders. During the project village malaria workers (VMWs), mobile malaria clinics (MMCs) and screening points (SPs) were established. Screening points which targeted mobile populations and migrant workers were located in fixed locations, such as bus stations and jetty terminals. Migrants could voluntarily have their temperature checked, be tested for malaria with a rapid diagnostic test, and receive adequate treatment if necessary between October 2012 and March 2015.

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was malaria positive rate among the group targeted by the intervention
- Although screening points screened fewer numbers of people compared to MMCs and VMWs, they yielded a similar malaria positive rate (**Table 8**)
- The combination of approaches (VMWs, MMCs and SPs) maximized the opportunities for migrants to obtain information and services while they travelled and at arrival to their destination community
- The location and timing of screening points, and the criteria for screening, are important factors in the resulting malaria positive rate
- Screening points also raise awareness of malaria among travelers, preparing them to recognize malaria symptoms and seek care more quickly in their destination community

Table 8. Malaria positive rate by year and service delivery approach.

Total testes and positive cases by service delivery approach					
Approach	Year	2012	2013	2014	Total
MMCs	Total tested	41550	61725	66584	169859
	Positive cases	1748	1082	1649	4479
VMWs	Total tested	21978	86316	48754	157048
	Positive cases	3290	5495	2669	11545
SPs	Total tested	884	1953	839	3676
	Positive cases	116	119	26	261

Malaria positive rate by service delivery approach				
Approach	MMCs	VMWs	SPs	Average
Positive rate	2.64%	7.29%	7.10%	4.90%

4. **Edwards, 2015:** Novel Cross-Border Approaches to Optimise Identification of Asymptomatic and Artemisinin-Resistant Plasmodium Infection in Mobile Populations Crossing Cambodian Borders

Prevalence of malaria evaluated by microscopy in Cambodia had fallen greatly to only 0.9% in the general population according to the Cambodia Malaria Survey 2010 (CMS2010), concentrated in certain high risk groups such as mobile populations and forest-goers (1.5% and 2.5% respectively). Cross-border movement of populations has been attributed to maintenance of ‘hot spots’ of high transmission along international borders. In response to the need to document the spread of malaria across borders, this nonrandomized observational study aimed to quantify the extent of malaria infection, including asymptomatic infection and artemisinin resistance (AR) parasites, in border crossing populations at specific sites on each of the Cambodian borders with Thailand, Laos and Vietnam, and to potentially identify “hot borders” in the country, even though control is very loose. From mid-August 2013 until mid-February 2014, booths were set up at each of the three selected official border points. Sample size was calculated at 3000 (e.g. 1000 samples per site), sufficient to provide enough precision ($\alpha = 0.05$, power = 0.9) to capture at least 3% prevalence. Any person (of all ages) crossing the border was eligible for participation. Participant temperature was taken using an infrared thermometer in order to test for presence of fever (temperature of 37.5°C). Malaria diagnosis was determined by rapid diagnostic test malaria antigen pLDH/HRP-2 combo (RDT). A single finger prick was used to complete the RDT and to produce a dry-blood spot (DBS) filter paper. If positive, they were treated according to Cambodian national treatment guidelines. UKaid sponsored the study and it was part of the Pre-Regional Artemisinin Initiative (Pre-RAI).

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was positivity rate (95% CI) among the group targeted by the intervention
- Between August 2013 and March 2014, a total of 3206 participants were included in the study and there were 103 malaria positive cases (**Table 9**)
- A very high proportion of *Plasmodium* infections were asymptomatic
- Of all positive fevers, 28 cases were identified by both tests, giving RDT sensitivity of 80.0% for symptomatic malaria identification. For symptomatic *P. falciparum* infection, sensitivity was 82.4%, and RDT identified 20 *P. falciparum* infections compared to 17 by PCR
- The high proportion of AR *P. falciparum* infections observed was particularly worrisome, as Laos was not formally acknowledged as affected by confirmed AR at the time of the study. Despite the small number of AR parasites identified, these data provided evidence of the frequent flow of border crossers carrying AR parasites between neighbouring countries, and was the first study to document the flow of AR parasites in

the region as well as to offer a feasible strategy to identify potential hot spots of resistance (Table 9).

Table 9. Malaria prevalence and proportion of positive cases found by RDT and RT-PCR.

Malaria prevalence evaluated by microscopy in Cambodia in 2010				
General population	High risk groups Mobile populations – Forest-goers			
0.9%	1.5%	2.8%		
Proportion of sampled individuals found to have <i>Plasmodium</i> infection by RDT				
	Thailand	Vietnam	Laos	Total
Nº of tested	1055	1007	1144	3206
Positive cases	1	10	92	103
Positivity rate % (95% CI)	0.1 (0 - 1.0)	1.0 (0.4 - 1.6)	8.0 (6.5 - 9.6)	3.2 (2.6 – 3.8)
Proportion of sampled individuals found to have <i>Plasmodium</i> infection by RT-PCR				
	Thailand	Vietnam	Laos	Total
Nº of tested	1055	1007	1143	3205
Positive cases	7	36	131	174
Positivity rate % (95% CI)	0.7 (0.2 - 1.2)	3.6 (2.4 - 4.7)	11.5 (9.6 - 13.3)	5.4 (4.6 – 6.2)

5. **Stratil, 2021:** Eliminating *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria: results from tailoring active case detection approaches to remote populations in forested border areas in north-eastern Cambodia

A key element of the Regional Artemisinin-resistance Initiative Two Elimination (RAI2E) is tailoring package of active case detection and expanding access to early diagnosis and effective treatment (EDAT) to remote populations in border areas with Laos, Thailand and Vietnam where the control is loose. A nonrandomized observational study was conducted to assess transmission taking place between January 2018 and December 2020 in this area. Proactive case detection was delivered through mobile malaria posts (MMPs) and outreach activities, and occasional reactive case detection (RCD) among co-travellers of index cases when feasible. MMWs were asked to conduct RCD if a confirmed malaria case has spent time in the forest in the previous two weeks. MMPs were placed at border crossings, at forest entry points or market places. MMPs operated seven days per week with standard operating hours between 7 am and 7 pm with operational flexibility to adjust to local population movement patterns. Everyone that passed their post was eligible for RDT testing. Malaria tests were conducted with *P. falciparum*/*P. vivax* rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) (SD BIOLINE Malaria Ag P.f/P.v, Standard Diagnostics) without prior screening for fever. Uncomplicated *P. falciparum*, mixed and *P. vivax* cases were treated with artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT). First-line ACT was artesunate-mefloquine with pyronaridine-artesunate used during prolonged stock-out of first line treatment. Single low-dose primaquine was given to *P. falciparum* and mixed cases.

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was number of tested and number of positive cases among the group targeted by the intervention
- MMWs under this project have contributed to testing 45% (80,988/180,732) of all people tested and detected 39% (1280/3243) of all *P. falciparum* cases and 72% (1280/1768) of community *P. falciparum* cases (VMW and MMWs) between 2018 and 2020 (Table 10).
- The results presented a successful approach to implementing tailored active case detection strategies. Key components of the project success were a combination of proactive and reactive case detection activities tailored to the local target population and context, operational flexibility, strong relationships with local communities, close supervision and quality assurance of service delivery and responsive systems that were able to adapt to changing circumstances.

Table 10. Malaria positive rate by year and by case detection approach.

Total testes and positive cases by case detection approach					
Approach	Year	2018	2019	2020	Total
MMPs	Total tested	5897	12839	12421	31157
	Positive cases	545	136	12	693
Outreach	Total tested	6906	19839	21389	47988
	Positive cases	343	170	20	533
Co-travellers	Total tested	604	768	123	1495
	Positive cases	46	8	-	54

Malaria positive rate by case detection approach				
Approach	MMPs	Outreach	Co-travellers	Average
Positive rate	1.57%	1.11%	3.61%	2.09%

6. Li, 2015: Malaria Imported from Ghana by Returning Gold Miners, China, 2013

The incidence of malaria in China decreased sharply to 0.18 cases per 100,000 persons in 2012. However, imported malaria among persons returning from overseas malaria-endemic regions was documented presenting a challenge for malaria elimination. In the Shanglin County there was a large outbreak of imported malaria among Chinese workers returning from overseas countries, mainly Ghana (vector species in the area *An. sinensis*). A nonrandomized observational study was conducted to analyze active malaria screening for 4 months during May 1 – August 31, 2013 for people with an overseas travel history during the previous years. Testing was not done at POE, but since China has a tight border control, it permitted the median interval between return date and diagnosis date to be 8 days (range 0–28 days; interquartile range 4–18 days). Diagnosis was done by microscopy and all positive cases with *P. falciparum* infection were treated with artemisinin-based combination therapy; persons who had no glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency and who were infected with *P. vivax* or *P. ovale* were radically cured with chloroquine combined with primaquine; and persons who had *P. malariae* infection were treated with chloroquine. The

study was supported by a grant from the Ministry of Science and Technology of China and the Ministry of Health of China.

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was attack rate among the group targeted by the intervention
- During the study period 4052 persons with histories of overseas travel were tested and 874 were positive (**Table 11**)
- Considering the remarkably increasing volume of cross-border travel, malaria imported from overseas countries is a new challenge for malaria elimination in China
- Measures to prevent mosquito bites and chemoprophylaxis should be addressed among groups at high occupational risk for malaria

Table 11. Attack rate and *Plasmodium* spp. for positive cases.

Results of attack rate in persons with overseas travel	
Nº persons screened for malaria	4052
Nº detected malaria infection	874
Attack rate (%)	21.6
<i>Plasmodium</i> spp. for the positive cases	
<i>P. falciparum</i>	827
<i>P. vivax</i>	42
<i>P. malariae</i>	1
<i>P. ovale</i>	1
<i>Plasmodium</i> spp. co-infection (Pf/Pv)	3

7. **Tseroni, 2020:** The Importance of an Active Case Detection (ACD) Programme for Malaria among Migrants from Malaria Endemic Countries: The Greek Experience in a Receptive and Vulnerable Area

Malaria was endemic in Greece until the 1960s and became a malaria-free country in 1974. Since 2009, imported *Plasmodium vivax* cases have been reported. In 2011, an outbreak of 36 *P. vivax* locally acquired malaria cases occurred in the Evrotas Municipality in the Peloponnese, southern Greece, where transmission occurs between July and October, has a tight border control and the vector species in the area is *An. sacharovi*. Evrotas was a historical hot spots of malaria in the past. To avoid reintroduction and interrupt local malaria transmission pro-active case detection (PACD) program was implemented from 2012 to 2017. Since 2012 other interventions have been implemented: vector control activities, such as Indoor Residual Spraying (IRS) and distribution and use of Long Lasting Insecticide-treated Nets (LLINs). In parallel with the ACD, and targeted Mass Drug Administration with anti-malarials for *P. vivax* was administered in 2013 and 2014 to all migrants from endemic countries residing in the specific area. To assess the ACD program an observational study was conducted. Testing was done in households by the field team, who screened for fever and other malaria compatible symptoms, and tested every suspected malaria case. For suspected malaria cases an RDT (with a *P. vivax* panel detection score of 91.4% at 200 parasites/µL) and/or blood sampling was performed. In the event of a positive RDT, the migrant was examined. In case of mild clinical symptoms, good clinical condition and mildly

affected blood test results, the patient was treated with Directly Observed Therapy (DOT) with chloroquine and primaquine, and further monitored. The median time period from the migrants arriving in Greece to the day of their first contact with the field team and their registration in the database was much higher for the years 2012–2014 (90, 60 and 10 days respectively), compared with the years 2015–2017 (5, 15 and 7 days respectively).

Key findings:

- The study was considered critical risk of bias due to observational study design
- The outcome was number of tested and number of positive cases among the group targeted by the intervention
- The program recorded a limited number of sporadic introduced cases and a steadily increasing annual number of imported *P. vivax* malaria cases in 2013–2017 (**Table 12**)
- The study population originated mainly from Pakistan, where *P. vivax* prevalence ranges from 2.4% in Punjab province to 10.8% in Sindh province
- No contextual factors assessed but the study showed that being undocumented usually makes migrants hesitant in their approach to health care services and that they welcomed treatment at home
- Along the program, surveillance indicators improved significantly over the years as no locally acquired malaria cases were reported in 2016–2017, even though the number of newly incoming migrants increased and no MDA was performed
- Although the PACD program in Evrotas contributed to the reduction of disease transmission in the area after the cluster peak of 2011 due to the implementation of multiple public health interventions, it was not feasible to accurately estimate the impact of each intervention

Table 12. Number of migrants screened, number of positive cases and median time in days.

Number of migrants screened and number of positive cases in Evrotas Municipality, 2012 - 2017				
Project year	Median nº of migrants screened	Nº of reported malaria cases	Nº of malaria cases among migrants detected through PACD	Median time (range) from arrival to registration, days
2012	920	17	15	90
2013	582	0	0	60
2014	496	0	0	10
2015	384	7	6	5
2016	857	15	12	15
2017	934	14	14	7
TOTAL	4173	53	47	-

Effects reported on prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention

Prevalence of infection among the targeted populations was reported only in **Bradley, 2015**, being 70.3% (CI 58.4-80.7) in the trip between mainland and Bioko in under 15 years old passengers. On the contrary, prevalence was about 22.6% (CI 17.3-28.6) between Bioko and mainland for passengers older than 15 years old.

The rest of the studies were included even though they did not report prevalence *per se*, rather other measures that were considered to be proxy estimates for prevalence and therefore relevant to the review.

To be able to compare results among the studies positivity rate was calculated for all the studies (**Table 13**). The positivity rate calculated for **Bradley, 2015** was consistent with the prevalence reported in the study. The highest positivity rate for all seven studies was observed in Bioko Island in 2013, being 70.3% (**Bradley, 2015**). Moreover, the four positivity rates found in Bioko Island classified by the direction of the trip and the age of the passenger were the highest ones found among all the included studies (> 22.6%). Only a similar positivity rate of 21.6% was found in Chinese workers returning from Ghana where they worked in the gold mining sector (**Li, 2015**). Except for the two years in Evrotas with no malaria cases due to the implementation of mass drug administration in the area (**Tseroni, 2020**), the lowest positivity rate (0.09%) was identified in the study using mobile malaria posts in remote populations in forested border areas of north-eastern Cambodian in 2020 (**Stratil, 2021**). Nevertheless, no specific information about which border these numbers were observed is given and nor if there were differences among the three borders. A bit higher positivity rates, around 1.5%, were observed among migrants' farm workers from endemic countries during the six years of the study (2012 – 2017) (**Stratil, 2021**).

In **Dar, 1993** very similar positivity rates between 5.0 and 10.0% were recorded for the four years (1988 – 1991) in Al Ain district, with a slight increase as the years went by. Despite the difference in years in which one study was done, positivity rates of a very similar range, between 3.0 and 13.0%, were found in Myanmar by **Kheang, 2017**, even though in this case there was a slight decrease during the three years (2012 – 2014) of the study. Despite the studies being conducted in the same borders, between Cambodia and Thailand, Laos and Vietnam, **Edwards, 2015** and **Stratil, 2021** showed different trends in the positivity rates found by official border points respectively and mobile malaria posts. The positivity rate found in border crossers from all nationalities and all ages between 2013 and 2014 was very different depending on the border, varying between 0.6%, 3.6% and 11.5% in the border with Cambodia and Thailand, Vietnam and Laos, respectively, as shown in **Edwards, 2015**. Positivity rates varied between 9.2%, 1.1% and 0.09% registered by mobile malaria clinics between 2018 and 2020 (**Stratil, 2021**).

Table 13. Positivity rate calculated for each study (total positive cases/total people tested)

Study	Test condition	People tested	Positive cases	Positivity rate (%)
Bradley, 2015	Bioko – Mainland / < 15 y.	165	63	38.1
	Mainland – Bioko / < 15 y.	101	71	70.3
	Bioko – Mainland / > 15 y.	1000	226	22.6
	Mainland – Bioko / > 15 y.	793	283	35.7
Dar, 1993	1988	15732	730	4.6
	1989	18022	936	5.2
	1990	18532	1282	6.9
	1991	16317	1483	9.1
Kheang, 2017	2012 / Screening points	884	116	13,1
	2013 / Screening points	1953	119	6,1
	2014 / Screening points	839	26	3,1

Edwards, 2015	Thailand / RT-PCR	1055	7	0.6
	Vietnam / RT-PCR	1007	36	3.6
	Laos / RT – PCR	1143	131	11.5
Stratil, 2021	2018 / Mobile malaria posts	5897	545	9.2
	2019 / Mobile malaria posts	12839	136	1.1
	2020 / Mobile malaria posts	12421	12	0.09
Li, 2015	Persons with overseas travel	4052	874	21.6
Tseroni, 2020	2012	920	15	1.6
	2013 / MDA	582	0	0
	2014 / MDA	496	0	0
	2015	384	6	1.6
	2016	857	12	1.4
	2017	934	14	1.5

Certainty of evidence

Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention

Since all studies have a critical risk of bias, have serious inconsistencies and have serious indirectness (except for **Bradley, 2015** which has a not serious indirectness), the certainty of the evidence was graded as very low. Therefore, we are very uncertain about the effect of TTaT POE on prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention.

Contextual factors

Acceptability and Feasibility

The acceptability of targeted test and treat at point of entry was reported in **Edwards, 2015** and **O’Sullivan, 2011**. **Edwards, 2015** assessed the number of refusals, defined as those that refused to participate after being approached and explained the purpose of the study, in border crossing points between Cambodia and Thailand, Vietnam and Laos. Numbers were recorded along with reasons for refusal where possible. Toward the end of the study period, it was clear that refusals made up a high proportion of those approached, as out of 4110 people approached, 904 (22%) refused. As a result, field teams attempted to record some observatory data on the refusal population including sex, approximate age group and mode of transport. Mode of transport was taken as a proxy for socioeconomic status (SES), with people in cars deemed as high SES and on foot as low SES. Main reasons for refusal (multiple answers possible) included not having enough time (51.6%), not perceiving themselves to be at risk of malaria and thus not requiring testing (40.6%), being scared to give blood (34.2%), or having an apparent language or cultural barrier (23.9%).

The **O’Sullivan, 2011** study conducted from March to April 2010, provided information on the feasibility and acceptability of implementing a new approach of surveillance, testing all travellers using RDT kits and offering treatment in Isabel Province, Solomon Islands. A variety of qualitative research tools were used, including Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and informal field observation. Participants’ answers suggested acceptability and support for such a system, however for it to be effective, RDT coverage would need to be scaled up and

should be prioritized at health facilities. In addition, positive cases should be treated as soon as possible and followed up by the malaria team. It is advantageous to provide free treatment for all these cases. On the other hand, results showed that screening all travellers entering Isabel Province at ports and airports was not viable due to prevailing financial and logistical constraints.

Feasibility of this intervention was also assessed in **Stratil, 2021**, which aimed to sustain and improve service delivery efficiency and effectiveness in terms of achieving high testing rates and detecting *P. falciparum* cases, as well as ensuring constant availability of test and treatment supplies. To achieve this, (i) quantitative evidence including testing rates, case clustering, and stock information, (ii) operational experience about the feasibility of operating service delivery sites in specific areas, and (iii) local knowledge about frequented forest areas and population movements were regularly reviewed by the project team to recognize emerging needs early on. These insights were used to continuously adapt the positioning of mobile malaria posts, target locations of outreach activities, timing of the service delivery and other operational aspects in collaboration with the National Center for Parasitology, Entomology and Malaria Control (CNM), local authorities and other implementing partners.

Mathematical modeling data

Three modelling studies from the same author were identified: **Silal, 2014**; **Silal, 2015²⁹** and **Silal, 2015³⁰**. Silal used data from the Mpumalanga province, South Africa, for the three reports which relate to the same study. For **Silal, 2014** a deterministic population-based non-linear ordinary differential equation model fitted to the Mpumalanga malaria data was used to predict the impact of the following interventions (alone and in combination): scale-up of vector control, mass drug administration (MDA), a focused mass screen and treat campaign (MSAT) and foreign source reduction. For **Silal, 2015²⁹** an hybrid metapopulation DE-IBM model was developed to simulate the impact of focal screen and treat (FSAT) at the Mpumalanga–Maputo border as a means to decrease the inflow of imported infections. This was the first model designed for this purpose in Mpumalanga and the first to do so since the call for malaria elimination in South Africa. For **Silal, 2015³⁰** a metapopulation structure was used to describe movement between five municipalities in the Ehlanzeni District on the eastern border of Mpumalanga and more importantly, movement between these municipalities and Maputo Province (MP), Mozambique. A stochastic, non-linear, ordinary-differential equation model fitted to the Mpumalanga and Maputo malaria case-notification data, was used to predict the impact of the following interventions (alone and in combination): scale-up of Vector Control, Mass Drug Administration (MDA), a Focal Screen and Treat (FSAT) campaign and foreign source reduction. In conclusion, it was found that while all strategies (in isolation or combined) contributed to decreasing local infections, none was able to decrease local infections to zero mainly due to the continuous stream of imported infections highlighting the importance of source reduction and a regional approach to malaria control and elimination. However, mathematical modelling may be used to inform government policy to tailor a strategy that captures the malaria situation not just in South Africa, but also in the immediate region, in order to inform feasible strategies to enable malaria elimination in the foreseeable future.

Summary of main results

Few studies contributed data to assess the effect of targeted test and treat at point of entry on outcomes and overall, the certainty of the evidence was very low. The studies expressed prevalence of malaria infection among those targeted by the intervention using different measures such as positivity rate and attack rate. The positivity rates reported in the seven nonrandomized observational studies ranged between 0.0 to 70.0%. The different settings and operational aspects of where the interventions took place may explain the range in positivity rates observed. In particular, how reachable the populations were, and the malaria burden in the origin country or region were important features of the studies. For instance, the fact that the highest positivity rates were reported in the **Bradley, 2015** study, where testing was done to boat passengers, could be due to Equatorial Guinea being a high-transmission area, but also due to the feasibility of identifying and targeting the passengers when entering or leaving the boat. On the contrary, the lowest positivity rate was identified in a low transmission area with loose border control where it might be difficult targeting migrants crossing the border, as seen in **Stratil, 2021**. It was also difficult to assess the impact of the intervention as none of the studies identified followed the targeted population to see whether treatment was effective, and recorded new malaria cases after receiving the intervention. Moreover, none of the studies had a controlled or randomized design, making it difficult to assess the impact of the intervention. Along these lines, two studies (**Kheang, 2017** and **Stratil, 2021**) showed a decreasing trend in the prevalence identified as the years went by, but there was no certain evidence that this was due to the TTaT POE implemented. In fact, it is not possible to randomly allocate people to travelling, therefore it will be a limitation of any study on this issue. With these results, it was not possible to know the relative effects (benefits and harms) of targeted test and treat at point of entry, rather only the yield of the intervention for estimating introduced malaria cases at borders can be assessed.

During the abstract and title screening many studies focused on border malaria were identified, nevertheless, the majority of them made a descriptive analysis of the situation without implementing any specific intervention, and many others tested people living in villages located in border areas, regardless of the last time they crossed the border. Given that we considered the implementation of the intervention on adults and children entering or returning to a country or subnational area, these studies were excluded.

Seven studies were included in this systematic review, all of them being observational. They were conducted in the following countries: Equatorial Guinea (**Bradley, 2015**), UAB (**Dar, 1993**), Myanmar (**Kheang, 2017**), China (**Li, 2015**), Greece (**Tseroni, 2020**), and Cambodia in the border with Thailand, Laos and Vietnam (**Edwards, 2015** and **Stratil, 2021**). All of them assessed targeted test and treat strategies, five of them (**Bradley, 2015; Dar, 1993; Kheang, 2017; Edwards, 2015 and Stratil, 2021**) at point of entry, and two (**Li, 2015** and **Tseroni, 2020**) right after entry. These two were included since the average time between arrival and test was relatively short making locally acquired infections unlikely. The approaches used to test the targeted population differ in each study, in those areas with a relatively tight and controlled

border, the test was done on a boat to travellers between the mainland and an island (**Bradley, 2015**); during a compulsory medical checkup after applying for resident or work permit (**Dar, 1993**); as part of active case detection to persons with an overseas travel history (**Li, 2015**); or in the preidentified household (**Tseroni, 2020**). On the contrary, in areas with a loosely controlled border, testing was done in malaria screening points, either located in fixed locations (**Kheang, 2017**), in official border points (**Edwards, 2015**) or in mobile malaria posts (**Stratil, 2021**). Maybe the implementation of TTaT POE can have a higher impact in tightly controlled borders, where newcomers are more controlled and surveillance can be easily applied.

Even though two studies had other interventions implemented at the same time as TTaT POE, they were included. **Stratil, 2021** attempted to do occasional reactive case detection among co-travelers of index cases. Even though it was not always feasible or possible, co-traveler investigations tested a total of 1495 compared to the 31157 tested in mobile malaria posts (**Table 12**). **Tseroni, 2020**, implemented targeted mass drug administration during the years 2013 and 2014, but there was no overlap in the study population as TDA targeted migrant residents in the specific area, whereas TTaT was in new migrant farm workers. The impact of the TDA during 2 years in the study timeline had an impact so the overall potential effect on the prevalence was not exclusive to TTaT POE. These results show the importance of combining targeted strategies to target an important high-risk population for preventing reestablishment of malaria in the area.

Three studies contributed data on contextual factors, highlighting the importance of acceptability, feasibility to scale-up and sustainability as key determinants when assessing a new malaria control intervention. Providing information, educational materials, raising awareness of malaria among travelers, preparing them to recognize malaria symptoms and seek care more quickly at point of entry, were considered acceptability enhancers. Three modelling studies were included, which concluded that different strategies in isolation or combination (ex. scale-up of vector control, mass drug administration, focused mass screen and treat campaigns and foreign source reduction) could contribute to decreasing local infections, even though none was able to decrease local infections to zero due mainly to the continuous stream of imported infections.

Targeted test and treat at point of entry can be used to identify “hot border” crossing points and discriminating them from border points representing less of a threat, allowing a better targeting of surveillance and intervention efforts by optimizing use of resources. It was also observed that the location and timing of the screening points, as well as the criteria for screening, were important factors in the resulting malaria positive rate. Updated information and continuous evaluation of the results would help to better target resources to identify malaria hot spots. Screening points identified a large number of malaria cases by specifically targeting high-risk populations such as mobile populations and migrant workers, in cases where routine monitoring was not efficient.

Imported malaria has been considered a primary concern in low-transmission or elimination settings, but the Bioko example shows that it can be a major factor in malaria transmission even in high-transmission areas²⁰. Different intensity of transmission between country borders or

areas can be considered a challenge. In fact, areas with low parasitemia have high vulnerability and receptivity to imported malaria.

Considering the remarkably increasing volumes of cross-border travel, malaria imported from overseas or neighboring countries or areas is a new challenge for malaria elimination. Therefore, using tailored packages of active case detection approaches in combination with the community-based passive case detection system will remain a key approach for the final phase of elimination of malaria.

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OTHER INFORMATION

Registration and protocol

The review protocol has been registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), registration number CRD42021240867.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Availability of data, code, and other materials

The review documents including data templates/forms and detailed data extracted from included studies are available by request and primary information on included studies available in MESA Track. Data analyses and code are not publicly available since they were conducted in a subscription-based software (Eppi-Reviewer).

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CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDIES**Characteristics of included studies***Bradley 2015*

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	December 2013
Location	Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea
Tight vs. loose border control	Tight
Peak transmission season	Year-round transmission
Baseline transmission intensity	In Bioko: 14% (2012), 28% (2013) and 18% (2014) prevalence of <i>Pf</i> in children from 2 to 14 years. In EG mainland: 59% prevalence of malaria in 2011.
Parasite species	<i>P. falciparum</i>
Vector species	Not described
Study design	Nonrandomized observational
Statistical power calculation	n/a
Clusters	n/a
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	Total: 2059 Intervention: 2059 Comparison: n/a
Participant characteristics	Passengers traveling by boat from Equatorial Guinea mainland to Bioko and vice versa.
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	RDT testing and treatment on a boat.
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	Not described
Drug and manufacturer	Not described
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Not described
Dosage	Not described
Diagnostic tool	RDT
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Not described
Duration of the intervention	1 month
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	

Prevalence of infection	<u>Measurement:</u> RDT
	<u>Value:</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioko – mainland: < 15 years old 38.1%; > 15 years old 22.6% • Mainland – Bioko: < 15 years old 70.4%; > 15 years old 35.7%
	<u>Sample size:</u> 2059

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection

Justification

“The study uses observational data. Although many observed confounding variables were adjusted for in this analysis, there could still be residual confounding”

“This study is likely to have underestimated the proportion of Bioko residents who travelled to mainland EG.”

Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Dar 1993

Study characteristics

METHODS

Study dates	1988 - 1991
Location	United Arab Emirates border with Oman
Tight vs. loose border control	Tight
Peak transmission season	November - March
Baseline transmission intensity	No local malaria transmission
Parasite species	<i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. malariae</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles culicifucies</i> , <i>A. stephensi</i>
Study design	Nonrandomized observational
Statistical power calculation	n/a
Clusters	n/a

PARTICIPANTS

Targeted population	<u>Total:</u> 68603 <u>Intervention:</u> 68603 <u>Comparison:</u> n/a
Participant characteristics	All new arrivals applying for resident or work permits.

INTERVENTION

Intervention	Microscopy testing and treatment during a medical check-up.
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	Medical check-up. Vector surveillance and control (larviciding on breeding sites and pyrethroids against adult flying insects).

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Drug and manufacturer	Chloroquine
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Chloroquine-resistant strains of <i>P. falciparum</i> were first encountered in UAE in 1984, when 5 cases of Yemeni origin were found to be unresponsive to standard treatment. They had all acquired the infection in Kenya.
Dosage	Standard chloroquine phosphate dose of 600 mg base at the clinic on day 0, and 600 mg base to be taken at home on day 1 and 300 mg base on day 2.
Diagnostic tool	Microscopy
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Not described
Duration of the intervention	4 years
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection	<p><u>Measurement:</u> Test with microscopy <u>Value:</u> positivity rate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1988: 4.6% • 1989: 5.2% • 1990: 6.9% • 1991: 9.1% <p><u>Sample size:</u> 68603</p>

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection

Justification

** No bias mentioned in the article.*

Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Kheang 2017

Study characteristics

METHODS

Study dates	2012 - 2016
Location	Myanmar
Tight vs. loose border control	Loose
Peak transmission season	May/June to October
Baseline transmission intensity	Not described
Parasite species	<i>P. falciparum</i>
Vector species	Not described
Study design	Nonrandomized observational

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Statistical power calculation	n/a
Clusters	n/a
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total:</u> 3676 <u>Intervention:</u> 3676 <u>Comparison:</u> n/a
Participant characteristics	Migrants entering into or departing from endemic areas.
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Test and treat (active and passive case detection) through screening points set up at fixed locations (such as bus stops, ferry docks, or informal border crossing points).
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	Malaria education, case management
Drug and manufacturer	Not described
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Not described
Dosage	Not described
Diagnostic tool	RDT
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Not described
Duration of the intervention	30 months
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection	<u>Measurement:</u> Test with RDT <u>Value:</u> positive rate identified in screening points <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2012: 13.1% • 2013: 6.1% • 2014: 3.1% <u>Sample size:</u> 3676
Risk of bias	
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection</i>	
Justification	
* No bias mentioned in the article.	
Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.	

Edwards 2015

Study characteristics

METHODS

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Study dates	2013 - 2014
Location	Cambodia borders with Thailand, Laos and Vietnam. Three official border crossing points, one from each of border.
Tight vs. loose border control	Loose
Peak transmission season	Not described
Baseline transmission intensity	Prevalence in 2010 was 0.9% (general population), 1.5% (mobile population), 2.5% (forest-goers).
Parasite species	<i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. malariae</i>
Vector species	Not described
Study design	Nonrandomized observational
Statistical power calculation	Sample size was calculated at 3000 (e.g. 1000 samples per site), sufficient to provide enough precision (alpha = 0.05, power = 0.9) to capture at least 3% prevalence based on real time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) analysis.
Clusters	n/a
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	Total: 3206 Intervention: 3206 Comparison: n/a
Participant characteristics	Mobile and migrant populations crossing the borders
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Fever screening, test and treat at official border points.
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	Not described
Drug and manufacturer	Treated according to Cambodian national treatment guidelines.
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Surveillance of artemisinin resistance within Cambodia is not currently linked to any cross-border activity.
Dosage	Treated according to Cambodian national treatment guidelines.
Diagnostic tool	RDT, qualitative RT-PCR
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Malaria rapid diagnostic test (RDT) pLDH/HRP-2 identified a positivity rate of 3.2% overall and sensitivity compared to RT-PCR was very low (43.1%). By border point, sensitivity was lowest at the Thailand border where no positive infections by RT-PCR were identified by RDT, though the number of cases was low, and from the Vietnam border point where sensitivity was only 22.2%.
Duration of the intervention	8 months (August 2013 to March 2014)
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	

	<u>Measurement:</u> Test with RDT at the border, PCR analysis
	<u>Value:</u> positive rate identified with RDT
Prevalence of infection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thailand: 0.1% • Vietnam: 1.0% • Laos: 8.0%
	<u>Sample size:</u> 3206 (RDT), 3205 (PCR)

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection

Justification

“Border points were not selected at random, they were chosen in order to be viable for logistic and operational reasons.”

“It was also observed that there was a population of border crossers unable to be approached at all. These were verbally reported by field teams to predominantly be people travelling in cars, trucks and buses, and thus assumedly of a higher SES compared to those crossing on foot.”

“There was also a selection bias in the study population (where participants were predominantly Cambodians) and was likely observed due to the fact of having the screening booths on the Cambodian side of the border”

Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Stratil 2021

Study characteristics

METHODS

Study dates	2018 - 2020
Location	Cambodia borders with Thailand, Laos and Vietnam.
Tight vs. loose border control	Loose
Peak transmission season	May - October
Baseline transmission intensity	Annual parasite index > 5 per 1000 population defined as high-risk communities to target
Parasite species	<i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i>
Vector species	Not described
Study design	Nonrandomized observational
Statistical power calculation	n/a
Clusters	n/a

PARTICIPANTS

Targeted population	Operational targets for mobile malaria posts were to test 20 people per week and for outreach sites to conduct two outreach activities per week. <u>Total:</u> 31157 <u>Intervention:</u> 31157
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	<u>Comparison:</u> n/a
Participant characteristics	Everyone living and working within the catchment area of the project sites with a focus on reaching the high risk population of adult males over the age of 15 living in forested border areas.
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Test and treat (proactive case detection) with mobile malaria posts at border crossings, at forest entry points or market places.
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	Locally informed outreach activities targeting more remote locations, case management, LLINs and hammock nets distribution.
Drug and manufacturer	Uncomplicated <i>P. falciparum</i> , mixed and <i>P. vivax</i> cases were treated with artemisinin-based combination therapy. First-line ACT was artesunate-mefloquine with pyronaridine-artesunate used during prolonged stock-out of first line treatment. Single low-dose primaquine was given to <i>P. falciparum</i> and mixed cases.
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Not described
Dosage	Not described for first-line treatment. Single low-dose primaquine for <i>P. falciparum</i> cases weighing < 50 kg (7.5 mg).
Diagnostic tool	RDT without prior screening of fever
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Asymptomatic population is usually missed by conventional RDTs with data showing that sensitivity of RDTs compared to polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in asymptomatic carriers could be as low as 18%. Sensitivity of RDTs among symptomatic cases has been reported to be insufficient as well, especially in cases with low parasitaemia.
Duration of the intervention	3 years
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection	<u>Measurement:</u> Test with RDT <u>Value:</u> positivity rate identified in mobile malaria posts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2018: 9.2% • 2019: 1.1% • 2020: 0.09% <u>Sample size:</u> 31157

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection

Justification

“As the size of target population had not been formally quantified, this case study could not determine changes in malaria incidence among the target population over time.”

Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2013
Location	China, Shanglin County
Tight vs. loose border control	Tight
Peak transmission season	Not described
Baseline transmission intensity	0.18 cases per 100,000 persons in 2012.
Parasite species	<i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. malariae</i> , <i>P. ovale</i>
Vector species	<i>An. sinensis</i>
Study design	Nonrandomized observational
Statistical power calculation	n/a
Clusters	n/a
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 4052 <u>Intervention</u> : 4052 <u>Comparison</u> : n/a
Participant characteristics	People returning from overseas malaria-endemic regions, mainly Ghana.
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Test and treat (active malaria screening) among people with an overseas travel history during the previous year. Median interval time between return date and diagnosis date was 8 days.
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	Entomologic investigations using light traps and human landing collections methods were conducted in the 4 villages that had a large number of confirmed malaria cases.
Drug and manufacturer	All persons who had <i>P. falciparum</i> infection were treated with artemisinin-based combination therapy; persons who had no glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency and who were infected with <i>P. vivax</i> or <i>P. ovale</i> were radically cured with chloroquine combined with primaquine; and persons who had <i>P. malariae</i> infection were treated with chloroquine.
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Not described
Dosage	Not described
Diagnostic tool	Microscopy
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Not described
Duration of the intervention	4 months, May - August 2013

OUTCOMES

Prevalence of infection	<u>Measurement</u> : Test with microscopy <u>Value</u> : positivity rate of 21.6% <u>Sample size</u> : 4052
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Risk of bias*Outcome: Prevalence of infection***Justification**

“Chemoprophylaxis and detailed exposure history in Ghana were not well documented because most returning miners lacked knowledge and awareness of malaria. In addition, recall was likely to have been poor, given that the miners had lived and worked overseas for a long time at the time of investigation”

Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

*Tseroni 2020***Study characteristics***METHODS*

Study dates	2012 - 2017
Location	Greece, Evrotas Municipality
Tight vs. loose border control	Tight
Peak transmission season	July - October
Baseline transmission intensity	Incidence of malaria among migrants estimated at 1.8% annually
Parasite species	<i>P. vivax</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles sacharovi</i>
Study design	Nonrandomized observational
Statistical power calculation	n/a
Clusters	n/a

PARTICIPANTS

Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 4173 <u>Intervention</u> : 4173 <u>Comparison</u> : n/a
Participant characteristics	Migrants from malaria endemic countries residing in the area and covered by the PACD program

INTERVENTION

Intervention	Test and treat (active case detection program). Screening with regular visits to households of migrants from malaria endemic countries for symptoms compatible with malaria)
Comparator	n/a
Background interventions	IRS, LLINs, targeted MDA for <i>P. vivax</i> (2013 - 2015)

Drug and manufacturer	DOT with chloroquine and primaquine
Drug resistance level in the sending area/country	Not described
Dosage	Not described
Diagnostic tool	RDT, confirmation with microscopy and PCR
Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test	Not described
Duration of the intervention	6 years (intermittently)
OUTCOMES	
	<u>Measurement</u> : malaria screening with RDT and blood smears and PCR on symptomatic patients
	<u>Value</u> : positivity rate
Prevalence of infection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2012: 1.6% • 2013: 0.0% • 2014: 0.0% • 2015: 1.6% • 2016: 1.4% • 2017: 1.5%
	<u>Sample size</u> : 4173 migrants screened (median)

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection

Justification

“A mobile population constitutes a limitation for the success of a PACD program; however, we developed several procedures to overcome the relevant challenges. We designed processes for locating, registration, verification and follow up for each migrant staying in the area for more than 24 h, leading to the development of our ACD databases and procedures.”

Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Characteristics of excluded studies

Study	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Bannister-Tyrrell 2019	³¹	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to villages. Not the correct outcome reported.
Betanzos-Reyes 2012	³²	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to a migrants hostel. Incorrect intervention: no treatment mentioned. Not the correct outcome reported.
Cairo 2017	³³	Abstract only/could not be retrieved. Cross-referenced article: Hiwat (2018).

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Canavati 2014	34	Cross-referenced article: Canavati (2016).
Carrara 2006	35	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to health centers.
Carrara 2013	36	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to villages.
Galindo 2019	37	Cross-referenced article: Galindo (2021) – Malakit Project
Grueninger 2013	38	Study focus area.
Hassanpour 2019	39,40	Incorrect population: test not done at POE. Incorrect intervention: no treatment mentioned.
Hiwat 2018	41	Study focus area – Malakit Project
Hustedt 2018	42	Cross-referenced article Stratil (2021). Study focus area.
Kamolratanakul 1999	43	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to a district.
Kasumov 2001	44	Abstract only/could not be retrieved.
Kheang 2015	45	Cross-referenced article: Kheang (2017).
Krisher 2016	46	Study focus area.
Li 2015	47	Abstract only/could not be retrieved.
Li 2021	48	Study focus area.
Liu 2016	49	Incorrect intervention: reactive case detection (RCD).
Lopes 2017	50	Poster only/could not be retrieved.
Manning 2018	51	Protocol only. Cross-referenced article: Lon (2015).
Moonasar 2016	52	Study focus area: Commentary article.
Moonen 2010	53	Study focus area.
Mosnier 2020	54	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to villages.
Nasir 2020	55	Study focus area: review.
O'Sullivan 2011	27	Not the correct outcome reported.
Pindolia 2010	56	Cross-referenced article: Pindolia (2014)
Raccurt 1997	57	Abstract only/could not be retrieved.
Rang 2014	58	Cross-referenced article: Edwards (2015)
Richards 2009	59	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to villages. Incorrect intervention: Bi-annual screening and treatment of households.
Rondón-Cotacio 2018	60	Study focus area.
Malaria Consortium 2021	61	Ongoing study with no results available yet. Project brief only.
Malaria Elimination 8 2018	62	Project brief only/could not be retrieved. Parental project: Malaria Elimination in Southern Africa (Elimination 8)
Malaria Consortium 2019	63	Cross-referenced article: Edwards (2015) Cross-referenced article: Lopes (2017)

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Anonymous 2018	64	MESA Track information only. Not the correct outcome reported.
Anonymous 2017	65	Project brief only/could not be retrieved.
Anonymous 2009	66	Not the correct outcome reported.
Anonymous 2015	67	Project brief only/could not be retrieved.
Silal 2014	28	Study focus area.
Silal 2015	29	Study focus area.
Silal 2015	30	Study focus area.
Villasis 2009	68	Abstract only/could not be retrieved.
Wangchuk 2019	69	Incorrect intervention: treatment not mentioned for the only positive case found.
Wangdi 2015	11	Study focus area: book chapter.
Wangroongsarb 2016	70	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to two sites (rural & urban).
Wen 2016	71	Study focus area.
Wickramage 2013	72	Incorrect population: a case study.
Wiwanitkit 2009	73	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to a rural district.
Wongsricha 2001	74	Study focus area.
Xu 2016	75	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to short and long migrants.
Xu 2021	76	Study focus area: systematic review.
Yan 2013	77	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to villages.
Zhang 2016	78	Incorrect population: population not mentioned. Not the correct outcomes reported.
Zhang 2016	79	Study focus area: positive cases reported from other sources (no intervention).
Zhou 2014	80	Study focus area: cases reported from the other sources.
Zhou 2016	81	Incorrect population: not targeted to POE population, targeted to internally displaced persons (IDP) camps and local villages.

Reasons for exclusion

Reasons for exclusion

Incorrect population	Not in adults and children entering or returning to a country or subnational area for work, military service, residence, tourism or to visit friends and families.
Incorrect intervention	Not parasitologic testing and treatment of confirmed cases.

	Other strategy such as: reactive case detection (RCD).
Incorrect study focus area	Study evaluates the efficacy of antimalarials, drug regimens/ dosing, diagnostic tests, supply chain, resource management, access to care, and/or quality of care and does not use the TTaT POE intervention design. Reviews and Systematic reviews.
Outcomes	Not the correct outcomes reported.
Cross-referenced article	Supplementary article to a primary study already included/excluded
Ongoing study with no results available yet/report could not be retrieved	Ongoing study, report not retrieved.
Abstract only/report could not be retrieved	Abstract, protocol or another document for which the full-text report could not be retrieved.
Protocol only/report could not be retrieved	

Ongoing studies

Study	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Malaria Consortium 2021	⁶¹	Ongoing study with no results available yet. Project brief only. Available in MESA Track ⁶ .
Anonymous 2018	⁶⁴	MESA Track information only. Not the correct outcome reported. Available in MESA Track ⁷ .
Anonymous 2017	⁶⁵	Project brief only/could not be retrieved. Available in MESA Track ⁸ .
Anonymous 2009	⁶⁶	Not the correct outcome reported. Available in MESA Track ⁹ .
Villasis 2009	⁶⁸	Abstract only/could not be retrieved.

⁶ <https://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/expanding-mobile-malaria-services-hard-reach-communities-northern-cambodia>

⁷ <https://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/extending-effective-malaria-control-and-artemisinin-resistance-containment-activities>

⁸ <http://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/e8-border-malaria-post-impact-evaluation>

⁹ <http://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/malaria-elimination-southern-africa-elimination-8>

Appendix 1. Search Strategy

Database: Ovid MEDLINE(R) and In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations <1946 to November 03, 2020>

Search terms	
1	*malaria/
2	exp malaria, falciparum/ or exp malaria, vivax/
3	malaria ovale.mp. or Plasmodium ovale/
4	plasmodium malariae.mp. or Plasmodium malariae/
5	1 or 2 or 3 or 4
6	Antimalarials/
7	Disease Eradication/ or elimination.tw
8	(tailored adj2 (intervention* or treatment* or strateg* or administration)).tw
9	(relapse adj2 prevention).mp
10	Presumptive adj2 (treatment or therapy).tw
11	focal adj2 (drug administration).tw or "focal MDA".tw
12	targeted adj2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration).tw
13	6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12
14	Diagnostic Techniques and Procedures/
15	(screening or screened or diagnosed or diagnostics or test*).tw
16	Point-of-Care Testing/
17	"rapid diagnostic test*" or RDT.tw
18	"parasitological adj2 diagnosis".tw
19	"Parasitologic adj test*" tw or "symptom screening".tw
20	"case detection" or PACD or ACD
21	14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20
22	(borders or frontier* or immigration* or immigrant* or migrant*).tw
23	point of entry.tw or Cross-border.tw
24	"Mobile population*".tw or "returning worker*".tw or "mobile worker*".tw
25	Emigration and Immigration/
26	Border crossing.tw
27	travel*.tw or Travel/
28	22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27
29	5 and 13 and 21 and 28

Appendix 2. Selection process and data extraction (methods)

Figure A2.1. Process Flow Diagram for Review Methodology

Process for including studies based on review question PICO criteria for synthesis and meta-analysis in parallel to systematic inclusion of contextual evidence that was integrated with results to support the guideline development panel in formulating final strategy recommendations.

Figure A2.2. Adapted PRISMA Flow Diagram for Study Synthesis⁸²

Table A2.3. Variables for data extraction from included studies.

Study design	Observational	Prospective Cohort Case-control Cross-sectional Qualitative
	Experimental	Quasi-experimental designs where clusters in the intervention arm and control arm are purposively (not randomly) selected Controlled and uncontrolled before-and-after studies Interrupted time series (ITS)
	Mathematical models	
Setting	Point of entry	Border crossing Airport Seaport
	Transmission	Transmission intensity
Demographics	Participant characteristics	Age Gender Other
Methodology	Diagnosis Diagnostic tool	
Treatment	Drug and manufacturer Dosage Drug resistance in the sending country	
Infectious agent	Parasite species	
Baseline data	Pre-intervention measures	Incidence Prevalence
	Background interventions	Vector control Insecticide-treated nets Surveillance
	Coverage of background interventions	
Intervention	Intervention population coverage	Target Actual
	Intervention arms	
	Control arms	

Outcomes	Epidemiological measures by sex	Number of positive cases found as a proportion of total imported cases Adverse events Prevalence of infection
Others	Contextual study information	
	Potential study bias	

Appendix 3. PRISMA Flow Diagram

*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers.

**Some of the reports assessed for eligibility have also been assessed for contextual factors and/or modelling.

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Systematic Review on Targeted Test and Treatment at Point of Entry

PRISMA flow diagram for Systematic Review of Targeted test and treat (TTaT) at point of entry (POF) to reduce importation of human malaria parasites

*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers.

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

